

RE4GREEN

Delphi Round 2: Feedback report for participants

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Executive summary

Achieving a just green transition in Europe, as envisaged in the European Green Deal, requires training across the research and innovation sectors on how to consider environmental, climate and broader justice considerations in research and innovation activities. Competency profiles can help ensure all actors have the skills, knowledge, attitudes and abilities to contribute to the green transition.

As an expert who provides education for researchers and innovators on environmental and justice issues, we invited you to participate in a Delphi study to find consensus on items to include in a competency profile for environmentally aware research and innovation. Your responses to the first round of the Delphi study were analysed, paying particular attention to divergent views, misunderstandings or suggestions for rephrasing. Your rating of individual competency items was analysed using descriptive statistics.

Consensus was predefined as having been achieved if greater than 69% of respondents agreed/strongly agreed to an item. The results of round 1 were pseudonymized and aggregated in a feedback summary report for survey respondents (Evans and Sabin 2025).

Round 1 results were discussed in an RE4GREEN mid-term consortium meeting (June 24th-25th 2025). The nine competency items that did not reach consensus and the corresponding open responses were discussed amongst the multidisciplinary consortium members and revised. Furthermore, RE4GREEN consortium members suggested removing the introduction to each competency “Researchers and innovators should...” because it was considered too normative rather than aspirational.

Revised dissensus items were presented for reconsideration to you in Round 2.

Open comments were again possible for all questions. Twenty out of the twenty-one experts who participated in Round 1 participated in Round 2. Of the nine adapted dissensus items, six reached consensus in Round 2 and three did not. A summary of the results of Round 2 are presented in this report. A third Delphi round was not necessary, allowing the competency profile to be finalized (see page 14)

Section 1: Agreement and disagreement on draft competency items

Agreement on reworded competency items for which no agreement was reached in Round 1 (consensus)

The nine revised competency items were resubmitted to the experts in round two of the Delphi survey. Experts were again asked to state their level of agreement on a 5-point Likert scale. Greater than 69% agreement was achieved on 6 of the reworded competency items, with even higher consensus thresholds (greater than 79%) achieved on 3 items (Table 1).

Table 1. Reworded competency items for which agreement was achieved amongst experts in the second Delphi round .

	% agree or strongly agree
1. Embodying Sustainability Values	
1.2 Supporting fairness	
Conduct research and innovation activities in a way that contributes to both social and environmental justice.	95,2
2. Embracing Complexity	
2.1 Systems thinking	
Recognise that sustainability in research and innovation involves complex, multi-faceted challenges, and therefore cannot be addressed through simplistic or one-dimensional solutions.	85,7
2.3 Problem framing	
Engage multiple stakeholders – especially those most at risk of potential harms – and consider their knowledge, perspectives, and priorities to support more equitable outcomes.	85,0
3. Envisioning Sustainable Futures	
3.3 Exploratory thinking	
Integrate sustainability principles throughout research and innovation processes, drawing on systematic and creative forms of inquiry (for example, through an ethics by design approach)	70,0
4. Acting for sustainability	
4.2 Collective action	

Support environmental and climate-positive initiatives within your research field*	75,0
4.3 Individual Initiative	
Model sustainable practice in research and innovation – including methodology, materials selection, and project goals.	70,0

Disagreement on competency items (dissensus)

No agreement was reached on the remaining three reworded competency items (Table 2)

Table 2. Reworded competency items for which no agreement (predefined as >69% agree or strongly agree) was achieved amongst experts in the second Delphi round

	<i>% agree or strongly agree</i>	<i>% neutral</i>	<i>% disagree or strongly disagree</i>
1. Embodying sustainability values			
1.3 Promoting nature			
Devise strategies for improving ecosystem health based on best available evidence as part of research and innovation.	61,9	14,3	23,8
2. Embracing complexity			
2.1 Systems thinking			
Examine the sustainability of research and innovation activities in relation to temporal, spatial, and contextual factors.	66,7	28,6	4,8
4. Acting for sustainability			
4.3 Individual initiative			
Appreciate how personal research goals can align with social and environmental priorities, at both local and international levels.	55	35	10

These three items are presented below (under their original domain and with their original numbering) together with the proportion of respondents who agreed/strongly agreed, were neutral, or disagreed/strongly disagreed and respondents' rationales for their responses (if given).

1. Embodying Sustainability Values

Reworded item

1.3 Promoting nature

Devise strategies for improving ecosystem health based on best available evidence as part of research and innovation.

Agree or strongly agree [% and respondent views and quotes]	Neutral and respondent views and quotes [% and respondent views and quotes]	Disagree or strongly disagree [% and respondent views and quotes]
61,9	14,3	23,8
<p>Three participants' comments reflected agreement with the content of the reworded item without reservations:</p> <p>“Developing strategies to improve ecosystem health can be considered an ethical duty in itself, whether one adopts a biocentric or an anthropocentric ethical perspective. Even from an anthropocentric standpoint, it becomes difficult to deny that human health is closely interconnected with the health of ecosystems.”</p> <p>“Environmentally aware research should promote ecosystem health (however defined) according to the best strategies (however best is</p>	<p>Just one neutral responder provided a comment, in which they worried about definitional vagueness and a lack of applicability to all research and innovation.</p> <p>“Improving ecosystem health is really broad and hard to define. Do we mean planetary health? What is the best wording here? Maybe not applicable for all R&I fields.”</p>	<p>For those who disagreed, they did so strongly – with all comments emphasizing that what counts as ‘evidence’ is often exclusive of more diverse and inclusive perspectives:</p> <p>“Claims to truth won't help us. Revealing the evidence chosen and the values behind it is likely more powerful. Name me any R&I action, I will go to google scholar and find evidence to support how it contributes to ecosystem health.”</p> <p>“Evidence here is left-open ended which is understandable. But in my personal research I've seen that co-creation of knowledge across different strata of society is key to enable</p>

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understood). This seems true a-priori, it wouldnt be environmentally aware research if it wasnt in done in pursuit of promoting ecosystem health.”

“it invites to use research already done about the subject”

Others agreed that the phrasing was better:

“I think the phasing is now better and succeeds to highlight that one needs to consider evidence if willing to promote the well-being of natural ecosystems.”

“It is now properly weighted.”

“A minor but reasonable edit.”

However, open comments were often less enthusiastic than the ratings indicated even for those who said they strongly agreed:

“Evidence is still not defined, but I'm not sure how to work around this.”

research to have a grip (not just on policy), but in people's lived experiences and realities. For me best-available evidence can very easily become conflated with evidence produced by very large market players which have an incentive in maintaining a status quo that is detrimental to citizens and people.”

“Best evidence is a Western-centred formulation and is a subject to knowledge domination and exclusion of alternative knowledge systems which might have more in-depth experience and knowledge of ecosystem health.”

“Evidence based strategies are submitted to data and information availability. However, it should also be considered uncertainty or data blindness due to lack of representation or not sufficient information about topics (unknown or uncertainty) as well”

“The use of "evidence" points to one specific form of knowledge, mostly Western positivism. I

<p>“Might not be relevant for all R&I”</p> <p>“Not all strategies have been tested in the past, therefore "evidence" for them cannot be provided.”</p>		<p>would argue for something like "based on the most appropriate available knowledge" instead.</p>
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Following a review of the comments by the research team, it was decided that the main point of objection – the need to incorporate diverse perspectives – was already covered in other competency items (*e.g. Consider the implications of global and local justice perspectives on research methodologies, priorities, and outcomes; Map out all stakeholders affected by a research and innovation project – including communities, industries, policymakers, and ecosystems; Engage multiple stakeholders – especially those most at risk of potential harms – and consider their knowledge, perspectives, and priorities to support more equitable outcomes; Mitigate against the environmental impact of research and innovation by considering alternate approaches (e.g., frugal innovation); Respect local and traditional knowledges and methods to address sustainability in research and innovation; Collaborate with multiple actors (such as policy makers and local communities) to shape sustainable approaches to research and innovation*). It was decided that this item would, therefore, not be revised and submitted to new rounds as this would not result in a distinct competency item.

2. Embracing Complexity

Reworded item

2.1 Systems thinking

Examine the sustainability of research and innovation activities in relation to temporal, spatial, and contextual factors.

<p>Agree or strongly agree [% and respondent views and quotes]</p>	<p>Neutral and respondent views and quotes [% and respondent views and quotes]</p>	<p>Disagree or strongly disagree [% and respondent views and quotes]</p>
<p>66,7</p>	<p>28,6</p>	<p>4,8</p>
<p>The comments of those who strongly agreed, reflected agreement with the content of the reworded item:</p> <p>“There is no absolute or universal idea of sustainability; rather, it must be discussed in relation to the timeframes considered and the specific characteristics of each context. In fact, the same action may be sustainable in the medium term but not in the long term, or it may be sustainable in one context but not in another.”</p>	<p>Those who were neutral still considered the item too vague to be actionable:</p> <p>“This feels correct but banal.”</p> <p>“I think this is still somehow unclear and vague, although the meaning that is behind this is important. Would still consider rephrasing, for example: examine the sustainability impacts of research and innovation activities including the influence of temporal, spatial, and contextual factors.”</p>	<p>One participant who strongly disagreed also commented on the vagueness of the competency:</p> <p>“I think it is important to include the contextual variable but I find the item still to vague. The formulation did not change in principle”</p>

<p>“I agree. We need tools for proper and comparable evaluations!”</p> <p>Or with the reservation that they agreed in principle, but the item was still vague:</p> <p>“I agree in principle although I understand the disagreement.”</p> <p>“Item is quite vague. Certain patterns can nevertheless be identified”</p> <p>“I can see how this is still vague, but I like the revision better.”</p> <p>One participant doubted about the verb choice:</p> <p>“I have a slight doubt on the word "examine", maybe better "investigate" or "consider"?”</p>	<p>“This one sounds too gaseous for me to find it useful.”</p> <p>“Quite vague. I think i'd be open to it if it was rephrased to be more specific - perhaps about understanding how ones specific research question fits into a system/program of research that could deliver sustainability (i.e., so research isnt siloed, or ends up with tunnel vision missing the complexity of sustainability problems). Sorry - that isnt phrased that well!”</p> <p>“Still vague.”</p>	
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Suggestions to improve the items overlapped with existing competency items (e.g. *“Recognise that sustainability in research and innovation involves complex, multi-faceted challenges, and therefore cannot be addressed through simplistic or one-dimensional solutions”* and *“Understand how alternative disciplinary and role-specific perspectives can complement one another”*). It was decided, as for the previous item, that the item would not be revised and submitted to new rounds as this would not result in a distinct competency item.

4. Acting for sustainability

Reworded item

4.3 Individual Initiative

Appreciate how personal research goals can align with social and environmental priorities, at both local and international levels.

<p>Agree or strongly agree [% and respondent views and quotes]</p>	<p>Neutral and respondent views and quotes [% and respondent views and quotes]</p>	<p>Disagree or strongly disagree [% and respondent views and quotes]</p>
<p>55</p>	<p>35</p>	<p>10</p>
<p>Those who agreed without reservations preferred the wording “social and environmental priorities” rather than the previously provided example of the “SDGs” which were considered too top down. Others provided their own examples, or just stated that they liked the new wording</p> <p>“I unfortunately think that the SDGs are too top-down to define a researchers activities, but they should be based on social and environmental priorities.”</p> <p>“I appreciate that individual initiative and its contribution to social and environmental well-being are being acknowledged.”</p>	<p>One neutral respondent considered the ability to align goals a question of capacity and expertise:</p> <p>“It is a question of capacity and requires expertise.”</p> <p>For other neutral respondents, the new wording did not provide more clarity, but rather raised more questions:</p> <p>Who appreciates? And what does it mean in practice?</p>	<p>One respondent who disagreed did not like the removal of the SDGs:</p> <p>“I like the UN SDGs. They are a reasonable benchmark”.</p> <p>Another seemed to misunderstand the question and did not realise the reference to the SDGs had been removed:</p> <p>“While I like where you head with this, I find a connection to the SDGs problematic because of the top-down Western-centred perspective SDGs are built upon”</p>

<p>“The goal of R&I should always be to make the bridge between research and real life problems.”</p> <p>“The research of our esteemed [anonymized] was published by the journal Nature or researches of our economists [anonymized] and many others, are aligned at local and international level of protests against multinational company which planned to build an ore processing plant on agricultural land without permits, which is also against our laws.”</p> <p>“I like the new formulation”</p> <p>Some agreed with the competency item, but still considered it vague:</p> <p>“This is better. But what are the social and environmental priorities meant here? I understand that the SDGs needed to be removed, but now this became a bit vague. Could the SDGs be an example in parentheses: Appreciate how personal research goals can align with social and environmental priorities (such as the SDGs), at both local and international levels.”</p>	<p>“Critical views will not necessarily align with dominant frames, yet they bring invaluable contributions appreciate seems vague. can we just Align personal research goals with these other goals? If they don't align, isn't that a problem?”</p>	
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<p>“Unfortunately this also seems trivially true. “Personal research goals [within Environmentally aware research] aligns with environmental priorities”. Does environmentally aware research have to align with social priorities? Now the statement is detached from the SDGs I suppose it would depend whose social priorities! That might look problematic if (for example) the social priority was pursuing economic growth at all costs (this is just an example, but it shouldn't be too tricky to imagine times social and environmental objectives could clash)”</p>		
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In the first round, some experts found the suggestion to align research goals with global sustainability goals, such as the SDGs, too prescriptive, too burdensome, or highlighted critiques of the SDGs. In the second round, the broader aim of alignment with social and environmental priorities was considered too vague. It was, therefore, decided that another rewording would not be fruitful and might overlap with the existing competency item “Identify research and innovation priorities which can contribute to a just transition towards a sustainable society”, which had already reached consensus. It was decided that this item would not be revised and submitted to new rounds.

Section 2 - Final competency items for which agreement was achieved amongst experts

Embodying Sustainability Values
1.1 Valuing sustainability
Acknowledge diverse perspectives and values concerning environmental and climate justice in the context of research and innovation.
Reflect on how personal values and perspectives regarding the environment influence decisions and actions taken during the research process.
Consider professional competency in research and innovation to include a responsibility to reduce environmental harms and increase environmental benefits. ¹
Uphold the do no (significant) harm principle and precautionary principle in relation to research and innovation. ²
1.2 Supporting fairness
Recognize the disproportionate impact of the planetary crisis on and within different communities due to coloniality and systemic injustice.
Consider the implications of global and local justice perspectives on research methodologies, priorities, and outcomes.
Support equity and justice for present and future generations in research and innovation proposals.
Conduct research and innovation activities in a way that contributes to both social and environmental justice.
1.3 Promoting nature
Acknowledge that research and innovation are embedded in, and can cause significant harm to, ecological systems.
Perceive the needs and rights of non-human Nature itself as a fundamental aspect of research ethics. ³
Practice care and respect towards the environment and other species, when designing a research or innovation project.
2. Embracing Complexity
2.1 Systems thinking
Recognise that sustainability in research and innovation involves complex, multi-faceted challenges, and therefore cannot be addressed through simplistic or one-dimensional solutions.
Be aware that the complexity of environmental, climate and sustainability challenges can be emotionally impactful.

Use systems thinking to determine the environmental consequences (including unintended consequences) of research and innovation activities.

2.2 Critical thinking

Recognize potential trade-offs between competing priorities (people, planet, profit) in research and innovation.

Evaluate the trustworthiness of information sources regarding environmental problems and potential solutions (e.g. technological solutions).⁴

Align project aims with alternative approaches towards growth and consumption which are informed by more sustainable and just economic models.

Build in opportunities for critical reflection throughout research and innovation projects to ensure continuous alignment with sustainability principles.

2.3 Problem framing

Identify common challenges, risks, and uncertainties related to the environmental and climate impacts of research and innovation activities in your field.

Map out all stakeholders affected by a research and innovation project – including communities, industries, policymakers, and ecosystems.

Openly and transparently communicate potential benefits and risks of a project to the environment, climate, and affected communities.

Engage multiple stakeholders – especially those most at risk of potential harms – and consider their knowledge, perspectives, and priorities to support more equitable outcomes.

3. Envisioning Sustainable Futures

3.1 Futures literacy

Envision sustainable outcomes and identify possible actions, innovations, and/or policies that would support these outcomes.

Anticipate ethical concerns of emerging technologies and their environmental and climate impacts.

Employ techniques for futures thinking, such as scenario development or speculative design, in relation to a planned research or innovation project.

Align immediate research and innovation efforts with long-term sustainability visions, adaptively balancing present needs and long-term sustainability objectives.

3.2 Adaptability

Consider emerging evidence on environmental harms caused by research and innovation, including the cumulative harms of all research and innovation activities.

Monitor progress toward envisioned futures and adjust strategies based on new insights or changing circumstances.
Mitigate against the environmental impact of research and innovation by considering alternate approaches (e.g., frugal innovation).
Participate in continuous learning activities to ensure professional skills are applicable to changing ecological and social circumstances.
3.3 Exploratory thinking
Understand how alternative disciplinary and role-specific perspectives can complement one another.
Respect local and traditional knowledges and methods to address sustainability in research and innovation.
Engage with key ethical debates regarding the environmental and climate impacts of a research and innovation project.
Integrate sustainability principles throughout research and innovation processes, drawing on systematic and creative forms of inquiry (for example, through an ethics by design approach)
4. Acting for sustainability
4.1 Political action
Recognise that sustainable approaches to research and innovation exist within the context of wider political systems.
Identify research and innovation priorities which can contribute to a just transition towards a sustainable society.
Be aware of the access to knowledge, networks and platforms that your role entails, and use this to promote environmentally and socially responsible action.
Strategically engage in policy dialogue and participatory processes for green initiatives as part of the research methodology or innovation cycle, when appropriate.
4.2 Collective action
Remember the importance of teamwork and collective action in tackling environmental (including climate) issues.
Demonstrate a capacity for accessible and collaborative work, for example through open science and FAIR data practices.
Support environmental and climate-positive initiatives within your research field
Collaborate with multiple actors (such as policy makers and local communities) to shape sustainable approaches to research and innovation.

4.3 Individual Initiative
Model sustainable practice in research and innovation – including methodology, materials selection, and project goals.
Recognise that everyone has a role to play in fostering sustainable approaches to research and innovation.
Be accountable for the environmental and social impacts of professional activities, and take corrective actions where needed.
Minor changes for flow/conceptual clarity: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Sentence structure simplified for clarity. 2. 'Apply' changed to 'Uphold' to reflect the need for ethical reasoning rather than simple application. 3. 'Other (non-human) species and of nature' changed simply to 'Nature', because Nature includes humans. Nature is treated as a real noun (and capitalized) to show importance. 4. 'Validity' changed to 'Trustworthiness' because validity has a specific technical meaning in many fields, whereas trustworthiness is broader and better reflects the meaning in this context related to the origin and potential biases related to information sources.

References

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